

Complex Formation of Copper(II) with some Sulphonamides derived from Amino Acids

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Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric study of the interaction of copper(II) with *N*-benzenesulphonamides, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(R)COOH$ (hereafter, LH) derived from amino acids, viz. serine ($R=CH_2OH$), threonine ($R=CH(CH_2OH)$) and methionine ($R=CH_2CH_2SCH_3$) indicated the formation of only 1:1 complexes of the type CuL^+ , $Cu(H_{-1}L)$, $Cu(H_{-2}L)(OX)^-$, or $Cu(H_{-2}L)(XOH)^-$, where $XOH=C_6H_5OH$ or H_2O . Formation constants of the complexes at 25 ± 1 , 35 ± 1 and $45 \pm 1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium having a constant ionic strength, $\mu=0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$), have been evaluated and the changes in the thermodynamic parameters associated with the complexation equilibria have been correlated with the modes of bonding of the ligands and stereochemistry of the metal ion.

INTERACTIONS of biological metal ion such as copper(II) with amino acids and peptide derivatives are of considerable interest as these often represent the role of metal ions in the enzymes¹. Sulphonamides derived from amino acids and peptides offer two or more potential binding sites for metal ions, specially for those belonging to the boarderline class with regard to their Lewis acidity^{2,3}. *N*-Benzenesulphonylserine (NBSS), *N*-benzenesulphonylthreonine (NBST) and *N*-benzenesulphonylmethionine (NBSM) formed both 1:1 and 1:2 metal-ligand complexes with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} and offered bidentate chelation to these metal ions using the deprotonated sulphonamido nitrogen atom and the oxygen atom (in case of NBSS and NBST) or the S atoms (in case of NBSM) of the R groups. The carboxylate group was found not to be involved in the complexation equilibria with these metal ions⁴. The present paper describes an equilibrium study of the interactions of these ligands with copper(II) at 25 ± 1 , 35 ± 1 and $45 \pm 1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium of constant ionic strength, $\mu=0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$), and correlation of the formation constants with the modes of bonding of the ligands and stereochemistry of Cu^{II} ion.

Experimental

The ligands NBSS, NBST and NBSM were prepared, purified and characterised by the literature procedure⁵⁻⁷. All the other reagents were of A.R. grade and their solutions were made in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified ethanol⁸.

pH measurements were made with a SYSTRONICS 335 digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) using a special glass electrode in conjunction with a SCE. The pH meter was calibrated using aqueous buffer solutions of pH 2, 4, 7 and 9 by the usual procedure⁹.

The experimental procedure for the equilibrium study involved the pH-metric titration of solutions of known amounts (0.008–0.01 *M*) of the ligands containing known amounts (0.01 *M*) of free mineral acid (here, HNO_3) in the absence and in the presence of known amounts (0.001–0.002 *M*) of Cu^{II} ions in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium maintaining a constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.2 M$) by adding requisite amounts of $NaNO_3$, with a standard (0.125 *M*) of $NaOH$ solution prepared in the same solvent medium and having the desired ionic strength at three temperatures, viz. 25 ± 1 , 35 ± 1 and $45 \pm 1^\circ$ (thermostated). Representative pH-titration curves are shown in Fig. 1.

Hydrogen ion concentration $[H]$ at any pH meter reading was obtained by incorporating corrections for mixed solvent⁹ and using the following values¹⁰ of pK_w of water, 14.00 (25°), 13.70 (35°) and 13.40 (45°). The concentration variables, viz. \bar{n}_H (average number of proton bound to the ligand ion L^-), \bar{n} (average number of protons released due to the reaction of copper(II) with the ligand, LH), and equilibrium concentration, $[L]$, of free ligand ion, L^- , were calculated by following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹¹ using the pH-titration curves (Fig. 1).

Visible absorption spectra of a series of solutions containing 0.001 *M* Cu^{II} and 0.005 *M* ligands (NBSS, NBST and NBSM) in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium adjusted to pH values corresponding to \bar{n} values of 0, 0.5, 1, 2 and 3 at 25° , were recorded with a Hilger UV-SPEK spectrophotometer. Absorption maxima of copper(II) in the presence of all the three ligands shifted to lower wave lengths with rise of pH of the solutions. Metal-ligand ratios in the complexes formed at different pH were determined^{12,13} spectrophotometrically. Only 1:1 Cu-ligand complexes with all the three ligands

Fig. 1. pH titration curves at 25°: (1) 0.01 M HNO₃, (2) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.002 M Cu^{II}, (3) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.008 M NBSS, (4) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.008 M NBSS + 0.002 M Cu^{II}, (5) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M NBST, (6) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M NBST + 0.002 M Cu^{II}, (7) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M NBSM, and (8) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M NBSM + 0.002 M Cu^{II}, initial volume of all solutions were 25 ml in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol, ionic strength $\mu = 0.2$ M (NaNO₃), titrant NaOH = 0.125 M in the same solvent medium.

NBSS, NBST and NBSM could be detected in the entire pH range studied.

Results and Discussions

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibria: In the absence of Cu^{II} all the three ligands (LH) offered a single buffer region pH (3–5) corresponding to the deprotonation (equilm. 1) of their carboxylic acid groups

and gave sharp inflection points at one mole of base per mole of the ligands (Fig. 1). The charges are dropped from the expressions for clarity. In the presence of Cu^{II} ions, such buffer regions corresponding to the deprotonation of

COOH groups were found to be lowered, indicating the involvement of the carboxylate moiety of the ligands in the complexation equilibria with Cu^{II} ion. A total of three protons ($\bar{n}=3$) per Cu^{II} were released with all the three ligands NBSS, NBST and NBSM (Fig. 2). With NBSS and NBST as ligands, the release of three protons occurred in overlapping steps in the pH range 2–7, while with NBSM as the ligand, the first two protons ($\bar{n}=2$) were released in overlapping steps in the pH range 2–5 and the third

Fig. 2. Average number (\bar{n}) of protons released from the ligand in the absence and in the presence of Cu^{II} ions at different pH.

proton ($2 < \bar{n} < 3$) was released in the pH range 7–9 providing a gap of nearly 2–2.5 pH units between the two buffer regions corresponding to $0 < \bar{n} < 2$ and $2 < \bar{n} < 3$. As only 1:1 Cu–ligand complexes were detected in the spectrophotometric measurements in the entire pH range studied with all the three ligands, the release of the first two protons in the presence of Cu^{II} was, therefore, attributed to the formation of the 1:1 complexes CuL⁺ followed by its deprotonation to form the complex Cu(H₋₁L), according to equilm. (2) and (3), respectively,

Hydrolysis of Cu^{II} (aq.) ion occurred at much higher pH values and could not interfere (Fig. 1, curve 2) the complexation equilibria (equilm. 2 and 3). The release of the second proton (equilm. 3) definitely involved the metal promoted deprotonation of the sulphonamido group (SO₂NH) of the coordinated ligands, L⁻, ions in the CuL⁺ complexes. The H₋₁L²⁻ ions, in the Cu(H₋₁L) complexes, stand for the ligand species which have lost both

carboxylic and sulphonamido protons due to complexation (equlms. 2 and 3) with Cu^{II} ion.

As the ligand $\text{H}_{-1}\text{L}^{\text{a-}}$ species could offer a maximum of three binding sites to Cu^{II} , viz. terdentate (O, N, O) chelation by $\text{H}_{-1}\text{L}^{\text{a-}}$ ions derived from NBSS and NBST using the carboxylate oxygen, sulphonamido nitrogen and the hydroxylic oxygen atoms of the R groups, and terdentate (O, N, S) chelation by the $\text{H}_{-1}\text{L}^{\text{a-}}$ ion derived from NBSM, it was, therefore, quite likely¹⁴ for the $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})$ complexes to take up a molecule of solvent (water or ethanol) for achieving a square-planar $\text{Cu}(\text{O}, \text{N}, \text{O})(\text{O})$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{O}, \text{N}, \text{S})(\text{O})$ geometry around Cu^{II} ion. The ambiguity as to whether the release of the third proton in the complexation equilibria with NBSS and NBST involved deprotonation of the coordinated solvent molecule or deprotonation of the alcoholic hydroxyl group of the R groups of the coordinated ligands, $\text{H}_{-1}\text{L}^{\text{a-}}$ ions in the $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{solvent})$ complexes, could not however be settled, as because none of these complexes could be isolated and characterised. The release of the third proton in these systems were, therefore, assumed to take place according to either of the following two equilibria (equlms. 4 and 5), where XOH stands for H_2O or $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$,

As there was no releasable hydrogen atom in the coordinated ligand species, $\text{H}_{-1}\text{L}^{\text{a-}}$ in the $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{XOH})$ complex derived from NBSM(LH), the release of the third proton ($2 < \bar{n} < 3$) was assigned to the deprotonation of the coordinated solvent (XOH) molecules according to equlm. (4). The constants $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}}$, $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}$ and $K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})}^{\text{H}}$ were evaluated by solving the formation function :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{a[\text{L}] + 2b[\text{L}]/[\text{H}] + 3c[\text{L}]/[\text{H}]^2}{1 + a[\text{L}] + b[\text{L}]/[\text{H}] + c[\text{L}]/[\text{H}]^2} \quad (6)$$

where, $a = K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}}$, $b = K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} \cdot K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}$, $c = K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} \cdot K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}} \cdot K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})}^{\text{H}}$ and \bar{n} = average number of protons released due to the interaction of Cu^{II} with the ligands LH. The \bar{n} and pL values were calculated using the pH-titration curves (Fig. 1) of the ligands in the absence and in the presence of Cu^{II} following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹¹ with the help of the equations,

$$\bar{n} = \{[(v'' - v')/(v + v')]\} \{ (A + B) / T_{\text{Cu}} \} + (1 - \bar{n}_{\text{H}}) \quad (7)$$

$$pL = \log_{10} \{ [1 + [\text{H}]/K_{\text{LH}}^{\text{H}}] (v + v'') \} / \{ (T_{\text{L}} - T_{\text{Cu}}) v \} \quad (8)$$

where, T_{L} , T_{Cu} , A and B stand for the initial concentration of the ligand (LH), Cu^{II} , free acid (HNO_3) and titrant base (NaOH), respectively; v , v' and

v'' are the volumes of B molar NaOH added to solutions (i) containing A molar HNO_3 , (ii) A molar $\text{HNO}_3 + T_{\text{L}}$ molar LH and (iii) A molar $\text{HNO}_3 + T_{\text{L}}$ molar LH and T_{Cu} molar Cu^{II} (where $T_{\text{L}} \geq 4T_{\text{Cu}}$), each of initial volume v , so as to get the same pH meter reading for all the three solutions; \bar{n}_{H} is average number of protons bound to the free ligand L^- ion. For the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{NBSM}$ equilibria the difference, $[(\text{pH})_{\bar{n}=2.5} - (\text{pH})_{\bar{n}=1.5}] \gg 3$, indicated the occurrence of equilibrium (4) independently of equilibrium (3). Consequently, it was possible to evaluate the deprotonation constant $K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})}^{\text{H}}$ by graphical solution of the relation :

$$\text{pH} = pK_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})}^{\text{H}} + \log_{10} \{ (\bar{n} - 2) / (3 - \bar{n}) \} \quad (9)$$

deduced from the formation function (6), assuming the concentration of free Cu^{II} ion and that of the complex, CuL^+ , negligibly small in the pH range corresponding to $2 < \bar{n} < 3$ (Fig. 2) for this system. For $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{NBSS}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{NBST}$ systems, the difference, $[(\text{pH})_{\bar{n}=2.5} - (\text{pH})_{\bar{n}=1.5}] \leq 1$, indicated overlapping of the deprotonation steps represented by equlms. (3) and (4) or (5). The deprotonation constants $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}$ and $K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})}^{\text{H}}$, for these systems, therefore, were, evaluated by graphical solution of the relation (10),

$$\frac{(Y)}{[\text{H}]} = \frac{1}{K_{\text{CuL}}^{2\text{H}}} \cdot (X) \cdot [\text{H}] + \frac{1}{K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})}^{\text{H}}} \quad (10)$$

where, $K_{\text{CuL}}^{2\text{H}} = K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}} \cdot K_{\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})}^{\text{H}}$, $(Y) = (3 - \bar{n}) / (\bar{n} - 2)$, and $(X) = (\bar{n} - 1) / (\bar{n} - 2)$, deduced from the formation function (6) assuming the concentration of free Cu^{II} ion negligibly small in comparison to those of the complexes CuL^+ , $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{XOH})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{OX})^-$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-2}\text{L})(\text{XOH})^-$ at pH values corresponding to $1 < \bar{n} < 3$. Preliminary values of $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and also of $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}$ were obtained by graphical solution of the relation,

$$\frac{(Y')}{[\text{H}]} = \frac{1}{K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} \cdot K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}} \cdot (X') \cdot \frac{[\text{H}]}{[\text{L}]} + \frac{1}{K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}} \quad (11)$$

where, $(Y') = (2 - \bar{n}) / (\bar{n} - 1)$ and $(X') = \bar{n} / (\bar{n} - 1)$, deduced from the formation function (6) assuming the concentration of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{OX})^-$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-2}\text{L})(\text{XOH})^-$ to be negligibly small in comparison to those of free Cu^{II} ion, and the complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{L})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{XOH})$ in the pH range corresponding to $0 < \bar{n} < 2$. Refined value of the constant $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}}$ was obtained by graphical solution of the relation :

$$\bar{n} = \{ K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} [\text{L}] (a') \} / \{ 1 + K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} [\text{L}] b' \} \quad (12)$$

where, $a' = \{ 1 + (2K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}} / [\text{H}]) + (3K_{\text{CuL}}^{2\text{H}} / [\text{H}]^2) \}$ and $b' = \{ 1 + (K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}} / [\text{H}]) + (K_{\text{CuL}}^{2\text{H}} / [\text{H}]^2) \}$ and using the values of $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}$ and $K_{\text{CuL}}^{2\text{H}}$ already determined. The values of $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $K_{\text{CuL}}^{2\text{H}}$ were subsequently refined

with the aid of equations (11) and (10) using the refined values of K_{CuL}^{Cu} .

Complex formation of Cu^{II} with all the three ligands involved the release of three protons per Cu^{II} . Though there were three releasable hydrogen atoms in the ligands NBSS and NBST (*viz.* the COOH, SO_2NH and C(OH) hydrogen atoms), there were only two such hydrogen atoms (*viz.* hydrogen atoms of COOH and SO_2NH groups) in the ligand NBSM. The release of the third proton in the Cu^{II} -NBSM system, therefore, definitely involved deprotonation of a coordinated solvent molecule in the complex $Cu(H_{-1}L)(XOH)$ according to equlm. (5). $K_{Cu(H_{-1}L)}^H$ for the Cu^{II} -NBSM complex was comparable in magnitude with the deprotonation constants of coordinated water in square-planar Cu^{II} complexes¹⁵. In the Cu^{II} -NBSS and Cu^{II} -NBST systems there were two possibilities, *viz.* equlm. (4) or (5), for the release of the third proton. The magnitude of the deprotonation constant, $K_{Cu(H_{-1}L)}^H$, for Cu^{II} -NBSS and Cu^{II} -NBST systems were quite close to each other indicating the identical nature of the sites of proton release in these two systems. The $K_{Cu(H_{-1}L)}^H$ values of these systems were nearly 10^8 times higher than the corresponding value for the Cu^{II} -NBSM system. This suggested that the equilibria corresponding to the release of the third proton in the Cu^{II} -NBSS and Cu^{II} -NBST systems were different from that in the Cu -NBSM system. It was, therefore, concluded that the deprotonation of the $Cu(H_{-1}L)(XOH)$ complexes derived from NBSS and NBST occurred according to equilibrium (5), involving the

release of proton from the alcoholic function of the R group on coordination to Cu^{II} .

Decrease of free energy ($-\Delta G$ values) associated with the proton-ligand and Cu^{II} -ligand equilibria indicated that all the reactions were thermodynamically favoured. With the exception of the formation of the Cu^{II} -NBSM complex CuL^+ , the enthalpy change (ΔH) for all the other equilibria were negative as expected for thermodynamically favoured reactions. Positive ΔH for the CuL^+ complex derived from NBSM was encountered probably due to the formation of a six membered chelate ring ($-N...Cu^{2+}...S-$), which was strained for not having any double bond. This unfavourable enthalpy effect was, however, compensated by the favourable entropy change (ΔS) arising out of terdentate (N, O, S) chelation of Cu^{II} in the complexation equilibria (equlm. 2) with NBSM as the ligand. Entropy change (ΔS) associated with the complexation equilibria (2) and (3) were all positive, while for the deprotonation equilibrium (4) or (5), the ΔS values were very close to zero or small negative or small positive. Therefore, the two initial equilibria (2) and (3) involved charge reduction and/or chelate ring formation. The ΔS values for the equilibria (2) of the Cu^{II} -NBSS and Cu^{II} -NBST systems were positive, but these were not as large as the ΔS values for the equilibrium (3). The stability constants, K_{CuL}^{Cu} (LH = NBSS, NBST), were found to be of the same order of magnitude as those for the Cu^{II} -acetate and Cu^{II} -propionate complexes, where chelation was not possible¹⁶⁻¹⁸. It was, therefore, concluded

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cu^{II} COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS ETHANOL MEDIUM, AT $\mu=0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$) AND ASSOCIATED THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Ligand	Constant	25°	35°	45°	$-\Delta G$ (25°) kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
NBSS(LH)	pK_{LH}^H	3.98	3.87	3.81	23	-8	100
	$\log K_{CuL}^{Cu}$	2.78	2.74	2.70	16	-6	32
	pK_{CuL}^H	4.45	4.41	4.36	26	-8	56
	$pK_{Cu(H_{-1}L)}^H$	4.95	4.78	4.62	29	-29	-1
NBST(LH)	pK_{LH}^H	4.05	4.01	3.96	23	-8	59
	$\log K_{CuL}^{Cu}$	2.65	2.60	2.56	15	-8	23
	pK_{CuL}^H	4.27	4.25	4.23	24	-6	68
	$pK_{Cu(H_{-1}L)}^H$	5.00	4.85	4.70	29	-27	4
NBSM(LH)	pK_{LH}^H	4.35	4.31	4.26	25	-9	55
	$\log K_{CuL}^{Cu}$	3.04	3.12	3.20	17	14	105
	pK_{CuL}^H	3.81	3.72	3.68	22	-17	17
	$pK_{Cu(H_{-1}L)}^H$	7.85	7.18	6.52	45	-120	-252

that the initial step of complexation of Cu^{II} with these ligands involved monodentate $-\text{COO}^- - \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ bonding by the carboxylate oxygen atom of the ligands with release of the COOH proton according to equilibrium (2), where the positive ΔS value was the consequence of the reduction of positive charge of the Cu^{II} ion by one unit to form the CuL^+ complex. Comparatively, large positive ΔS values for equilibrium (3) were definitely due to chelation of the complexed Cu^{II} ion by the sulphonamido nitrogen atom and hydroxylic oxygen atom of the coordinated ligand L^- ion in these complexes, with the release of a proton, preferably from the sulphonamido (SO_2NH) group due to the electron withdrawing effect of the two sulphonamido oxygen atoms, ultimately producing the electroneutral complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{XOH})$. The third step in the complexation equilibria (equilm. 4 or 5) involved creation of charged species, viz. H^+ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-2}\text{L})(\text{XOH})^-$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{OX})^-$ out of electro-neutral complexes. Consequently, the ΔS values were not as favourable as those were for the equilibria (2) and (3). Much higher positive ΔS values associated with equilibrium (2) for the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{NBSM}$ system suggested the reduction of charge together with the formation of chelate rings. Small positive ΔS values for equilibrium (3) for the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{NBSM}$ system suggested the absence of any chelation in this step, which therefore, involved only charge neutralisation of the CuL^+ complex. Subsequent release of proton (equilm. 4) from $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{L})(\text{XOH})$ complex involved the creation of charged species, consequently ΔS was negative.

The stability of CuL^+ complexes were found to be in the order: $\text{NBSM} > \text{NBSS} > \text{NBST}$. Higher or basicity coupled with π -acidity of the sulphur donor atom of the CH_2S moiety of the R group of NBSM enabled it to form stronger bonds with the Cu^{II} ion. Lower stability of the NBST complex was probably due to some unfavourable steric effect exerted by the methyl group adjacent to the

alcoholic hydroxyl function in the R group of the ligand. Closer magnitude of $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}$ values for the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{NBSS}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{NBST}$ complexes suggested the occurrence of the same type of processes, i.e., coordination of the sulphonamido nitrogen and hydroxylic oxygen atoms to Cu^{II} in the CuL^+ complexes with release of the sulphonamido proton (equilm. 3). Higher $K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{H}}$ for the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} - \text{NBSM}$ complex was the manifestation of the π -acidity of the sulphur donor atom in the R group of NBSM.

References

1. H. SIGEL and B. MARTIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, 82, 885.
2. G. N. MUKHERJEE and A. CHAKRABORTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 749.
3. G. N. MUKHERJEE, P. DHAR and A. SEN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 8022.
4. G. N. MUKHERJEE and P. DHAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 79.
5. J. S. FRUTON and H. T. CLARKE, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1984, 106, 667.
6. E. ABDARHALDEN and A. BAHN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 210, 246.
7. S. GURIN and H. T. CLARKE, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1984, 107, 895.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", E.L.B.S., London, 1969, p. 167.
9. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
10. J. LURIE, "Hand Book of Analytical Chemistry", MIR Publishers, Moscow, 1978, p. 198.
11. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904; 1959, 3397.
12. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
13. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, 9, 119.
14. C. J. BALLHAUSSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 193.
15. A. E. MARTELL, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1968, 17, 129.
16. S. RAMAMURTHY and M. SANTAPPA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 2893.
17. L. MAGON, A. CASSOL and R. PORTANOVA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 2, 285.
18. J. W. BUNTING and K. M. THONG, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, 48, 1654.